

Utility of the ELISPOT Assay for Monitoring BK Polyomavirus Immune Response in Kidney Transplant Recipients: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Apurva Parekh¹, Mayur Patil², Dev Patel³

¹Associate Professor, Department of Nephrology, Dr M.K. Shah Medical College and Research Centre

²Assistant Professor, Department of Nephrology, Dr M.K. Shah Medical College and Research Centre

³Assistant Professor, Department of Nephrology, Dr M.K. Shah Medical College and Research Centre

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Apurva Parekh

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Abstract:

The study emphasizes the role of the Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Spot (ELISPOT) assay in assessing the immune response against BK virus (BKV) infection after kidney transplantation. This is crucial because BKV infection can lead to BKV nephropathy (BKVAN), which can result in graft dysfunction and potential allograft loss. The ELISPOT assay helps evaluate the recipient's immune response by detecting interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) production in response to BKV. According to the systematic review and meta-analysis, ELISPOT has shown a high sensitivity (0.95) and specificity (0.88), indicating its strong potential as a tool for identifying patients at risk of active BKV infection. In particular, patients with negative ELISPOT results had a significantly higher risk of active BKV replication (odds ratio of 71.9), and there was a clear distinction between active and resolving BKV infections based on the number of IFN- γ producing cells. Thus, integrating the ELISPOT assay with viral load monitoring could help tailor immunosuppressive therapy, balancing the need to prevent transplant rejection while managing the risk of BKV replication. This dual approach could potentially improve patient outcomes by providing a more precise strategy for managing BKV infection in kidney transplant recipients.

Keywords: BK Polyomavirus, Renal, Transplant and ELISPOT.

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Introduction

The risk of BKV infection, particularly BKV-associated nephropathy (BKVAN), remains a significant challenge despite advancements in immunosuppressive therapies and transplantation immunology [1]. BKV replication can result from either reactivation or primary infection. After kidney transplantation, a large proportion of patients experience early BKV replication, manifesting as BK viremia (30–40%) [2]. While some of these patients may contain the virus, others progress to BK viremia (10–20%), and a smaller percentage (1–10%) develop BKVAN, which can lead to graft dysfunction and loss [3].

The incidence of BKVAN tends to be higher in patients receiving more potent immunosuppressive therapies, which is increasingly common as the transplant population includes more patients with higher immunological risks. The challenge here is balancing the immunosuppressive therapy to prevent organ rejection while trying to manage the risk of BKV replication [4]. Lowering immunosuppressive drugs to treat BKVAN is the standard approach; however, this strategy raises the risk of transplant rejection due to heightened immune responses. Given the complexity of managing BKV replication and

the risk of rejection, there is an urgent need for effective treatments for BKVAN.

Currently, reducing immunosuppressive therapy remains the primary management option, but further research is required to identify additional therapeutic strategies, such as antiviral agents, or more targeted approaches that balance the risk of infection with transplant rejection [5]. The lack of reliable tools to monitor a patient's immune response to BKV during immunosuppressive therapy is a critical gap in managing kidney transplant recipients. The cytokine interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) plays a crucial role in the antiviral immune response, including against BKV [6]. Its expression is upregulated in response to BKV infection, making it a useful biomarker for assessing the immune response. The enzyme-linked immunosorbent spot (ELISPOT) assay is a promising tool developed to evaluate the frequency of IFN- γ -producing T lymphocytes [7]. By assessing the immune response to BKV, the ELISPOT assay helps stratify patients into risk groups based on their immune status. Patients with a negative BKV ELISPOT, indicating a weak or in-

sufficient immune response against BKV, are considered at high risk. These patients are more likely to experience persistent BK viremia and develop BKV-associated nephropathy (BKVAN), which can lead to graft dysfunction and loss [8].

On the other hand, patients with a positive BKV ELISPOT show a more robust immune response, suggesting that their immune system is adequately controlling BKV replication. This differentiation can be essential for tailoring immunosuppressive therapy. Those with a strong immune response (positive ELISPOT) might tolerate a lower dose of immunosuppressive drugs without increasing the risk of transplant rejection, whereas those with a negative ELISPOT may require more intensive monitoring and potential adjustments to immunosuppressive therapy. The ability to monitor BKV-specific immune responses with ELISPOT could be pivotal for improving patient outcomes by identifying those at risk for BKVAN early, thereby allowing for more informed decision-making in managing immunosuppressive therapy [9].

The objective of the present study was to systematically analyze publications describing the clinical use of IFN- γ ELISPOT in kidney transplant recipients who experienced BKV replication, and provide an evidence-based assessment on whether this ELISPOT assay can be applied in clinical practice.

Materials and Methods

Data sources and searches: The systematic review follows the PRISMA [10] (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines, which are widely used to ensure transparency and rigor in the reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses. The literature search was conducted in three major databases—MEDLINE, Scopus, and the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials—on 21 August 2024, to identify studies that evaluated the use of the ELISPOT assay for monitoring BKV infection.

In addition to database searches, the review also included a manual search of references from the retrieved articles, ensuring that all relevant studies were considered. This thorough search strategy increases the comprehensiveness and reliability of the findings. By adhering to the PRISMA guidelines, the review provides a transparent and reproducible summary of the existing evidence on the diagnostic performance and clinical relevance of the ELISPOT assay in the context of BKV infection in kidney transplant recipients. For MEDLINE, we used the following Medical Subject Heading terms (MeSH): ("Enzyme-Linked Immunospot Assay"[Mesh]) AND "Kidney Transplantation"[Mesh]. For Scopus, the following search terms were applied: TITLE-ABS-KEY (ELISPOT AND Transplantation). For the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials,

we use the MeSH descriptor which exploded all trees of [Enzyme-Linked Immunospot Assay] and [Kidney Transplantation].

Selection of studies: The systematic review included both retrospective and prospective studies that specifically investigated the use of the ELISPOT assay for monitoring immune responses against BKV in kidney transplantation. To ensure the relevance of the included studies, only those that directly correlated the ELISPOT results to BKV-related clinical endpoints (e.g., BKV replication or development of BKV-associated nephropathy) were considered for the meta-analysis. Both pre-transplantation and post-transplantation studies were included, as the ELISPOT assay can be applied at different stages of transplantation. The studies included in the meta-analysis were required to report the cut-off values for the ELISPOT assay to assess its sensitivity and specificity. Additionally, studies had to provide data on the total number of patients with and without BKV replication, as well as the number of patients with positive or negative ELISPOT results. If this information was not explicitly reported, it needed to be calculable from the available data in the manuscripts.

For the analysis of the standardized mean difference (SMD) regarding IFN- γ -producing cells, studies that provided actual counts of IFN- γ -producing cells, either on an individual patient level or as a mean for the study population, were included. Lastly, only studies with sufficient methodological detail, following the Standards for Reporting of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies (STARD) 2015 guidelines, were included to ensure the quality and reliability of the data. This rigorous selection process ensured that the studies included in the meta-analysis provided reliable and comprehensive data to assess the performance of the ELISPOT assay in monitoring BKV infection and guiding immunosuppressive therapy in kidney transplant recipients.

Data extraction and quality assessment: The following data were extracted from each study: author's name, year of publication, country of origin, type of study, timing of ELISPOT testing, the total number of patients with positive and negative ELISPOT tests, and the number of patients with BKV replication in each group. The cutoff for a positive ELISPOT assay in each study and the patients' actual number of IFN- γ producing cells were included for the analyses. In the post-transplantation ELISPOT studies, the ELISPOT results were retrieved from 2 time points. The first measurements were at the time that BKV replication was diagnosed or when viral load was actively increasing, which in our review we defined as having the "active BKV infection". The second ELISPOT results were collected when the infection was resolving or closest to the time of BK viral clearance, which we defined as "resolving BKV

infection". If the ELISPOT values at these time points were not available, the actual values in these studies were not included in the analyses. Every type of BKV antigen used for stimulating the recipient's peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) was covered, including large T, small t, virion protein 1 (VP1), VP2, VP3, and mixed BK antigen. Patient characteristics, including immunosuppressive regimen and allograft function, were obtained from each study if available.

Analysis: As global measures of accuracy across all test threshold, we calculated the pooled diagnostic odds ratio (OR) for active BKV infection in patients with positive IFN- γ ELISPOT compared with patients who had negative IFN- γ ELISPOT, and the area under the summary receiver operating characteristic (SROC) curve. In calculating the OR, a continuity correction was applied to all cells in studies with any zero-cell count. The standardized mean difference (SMD) of the IFN- γ producing cells from patients with active and resolving BKV infection were calculated after normalizing the actual value of

the ELISPOT assay to the number of IFN- γ producing cells per 3×10^5 PBMC. For studies not providing mean and standard deviation (SD), the estimation method was applied.

All pooled estimates were calculated using random effects models. A funnel plot was used to demonstrate possible publication bias, and Egger's method was used to test for asymmetry of the funnel plot. The existence of heterogeneity among study effect sizes was examined using the I² index and the Q-test p-value. An I² index higher than 75% reflects medium to high heterogeneity. The analyses were performed using Stata Statistical Software Release 21.0.

Results

A total of 651 articles were initially identified, and after excluding irrelevant and duplicated studies, 127 articles underwent full-text review. Nine articles met the inclusion criteria and were included in the meta-analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the study

All these studies evaluated the relationship between the IFN- γ ELISPOT assay and BKV infection in the post-transplantation period, with two studies also assessing pre-transplantation measurements. The studies varied in study design and technical approach, including differences in the BK viral antigens used for the ELISPOT assay, such as large

T antigen (7 studies), small t antigen (4 studies), VP1 antigen (6 studies), VP2 antigen (4 studies), VP3 antigen (4 studies), and mixed antigens (3 studies). Additionally, the definitions of BKV infection differed across studies, ranging from positive decoy cells in urine, viremia, and viremia, to full-blown BKVAN. The number of PBMCs used in

the ELISPOT assay also varied, and to facilitate comparison, the analysis standardized the results to the number of IFN- γ -producing cells per 3×10^5 PBMCs.

The QUADAS-2 tool was used to assess the risk of bias in each study, ensuring that only studies with adequate methodological rigor were included in the analysis and the QUADAS-2 risk of bias assessment for each study is shown in (Table 1 and Table 2).

Table 1: Summary of studies reporting data in BKV-infected kidney transplant recipients

Authors & year	Country of origin	Timing of ELISPOT	Patient with active BKV infection (n)	Patients with resolving BKV infection	Onset of BK viremia (months after transplantation)	Definition of BKV infection
Binggeli et al. 2007[11]	Switzerland	Post-transplantation	22	20	NA	Viremia
Prosser et al. 2008[12]	USA	Post-transplantation	8	8	16 \pm 11	BKV- associate nephropathy
Chakera et al. 2011[13]	UK	Post-transplantation	9	9	NA	Urine decoy cell and viremia
Schachtner et al. 2011[14]	Germany	Post-transplantation	18	17	14 \pm 18	Viremia
Costa et al. 2014[15]	Italy	Post-transplantation	12	-	NA	Viremia
Schachtner et al. 2014[16]	Germany	Post-transplantation	12	12	2 \pm 1	Viruria or viremia
Mutlu et al. 2015[17]	Turkey	Pre- and post-transplantation	12	6	5 \pm 2	Viremia
Schachtner et al. 2015[18]	Germany	Pre- and post-transplantation	16	-	3 \pm 2	Viremia
Bae et al. 2020[19]	South Korea	Post-transplantation	17	34	13 \pm 14	Viremia

Table 2: QUADAS-2 for risk of bias assessment.

Authors and year of publication	Risk of bias Patient selection	Index test	Reference standard	Flow and timing	Applicability concerns Patient selection	Index test	Reference standard
Binggeli et al. 2007	Low	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Prosser et al. 2008	Unclear	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Chakera et al. 2011	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Schachtner et al. 2011	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Costa et al. 2014	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Schachtner et al. 2014	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Mutlu et al. 2015	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Schachtner et al. 2015	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Bae et al. 2020	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

All studies evaluated the relationship between the IFN- γ ELISPOT assay and BKV infection in the post-transplantation period. Two of these nine studies also assessed pre-transplantation measurements.

The nine studies varied in study design and technical approach. First, the BK viral antigens used for each study varied, including large T antigen in 7 studies, small t antigen in 4 studies, VP1 antigen in 6 studies, VP2 antigen in 4 studies, VP3 antigen in 4 studies,

and mixed antigen in 3 studies. All studies measured IFN- γ as the cytokine for the T lymphocyte-specific immune response against BK viral antigens.

Second, the definitions of BKV infection among these studies were different, and ranged from positive decoy cells in urine, viremia, viremia, to full-blown BKVAN. Third, the number of PBMCs used have resolving BKV infection (diagnostic OR 71.91, 95%-CI 30.96–167.05, p-value < 0.001, I² = 0%, Q-test p-value = 0.80; Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Diagnostic odds ratio of patients with negative compared to positive BKV-specific IFN- γ for having active BKV infection.

Considering that only 2 studies evaluated the BKV ELISPOT assay before kidney transplantation, we decided to focus our analyses on publications reporting post-transplantation studies. The included studies used varying definitions of BKV infection including decoy cell-positive, viremia, viremia, or BKVAN. Each study measured IFN- γ ELISPOT response to BK viral antigen and correlated this with the clinical course of the patients, which was classified as "active BKV infection" and "resolving BKV infection". Four studies reported sufficient information on the ELISPOT cut-off values, the number of patients with positive and negative ELISPOT test results, and the BKV infection status at the time that ELISPOT was tested, which allowed us to perform meta-analysis for the diagnostic efficacy. The pooled ELISPOT values in patients

with active BKV infection compared with patients who had resolving BKV infection was formulated from 7 studies which could also be used for the calculation of the SMD. One study did not report adequate information on the timing of the ELISPOT assay and patients' BKV status, and therefore was excluded from the final analysis.

Discussion

This study provides valuable insights into the utility of the IFN- γ ELISPOT assay for assessing T cell responsiveness to BK virus (BKV) infection in kidney transplant recipients. It demonstrates that the assay can effectively discriminate between patients with active BKV infection and those with resolving infection. The finding that negative IFN- γ ELISPOT

results correlate with a 71.9-fold higher risk of active BKV infection is particularly noteworthy, as it highlights the potential of the test for identifying high-risk patients. However, the low negative likelihood ratio (NLR) of 0.09 suggests that a negative result should raise suspicion for exclusion of active infection, but it may not definitively rule out the presence of active BKV infection. On the other hand, the positive likelihood ratio (PLR) of 6.3 indicates that a positive result may be useful in identifying patients who are more likely to have active infection, though it may not be sufficient to confirm it conclusively. Overall, the IFN- γ ELISPOT assay shows promise in identifying patients at higher risk for active BKV infection but may need to be combined with other diagnostic methods for comprehensive clinical decision-making.

BKV is an important cause of kidney allograft loss due to the lack of effective treatment. The current practice is to prevent significant BKV replication, including the surveillance for early BK viremia or viruria and minimizing risk factors that are known for BKV reactivation [20]. Besides the well-recognized risks such as intensified immunosuppression, the degree of human leukocyte antigen (HLA) mismatches, and kidney allograft ischemic reperfusion injury, more recent evidence suggests that the mismatch between high donor BKV IgG sero-reactivity and low recipient sero-reactivity significantly increases the risk of BK viremia. Moreover, the lack of donor-specific BKV genotype neutralizing antibody in the recipient also significantly associated with BKV infection after transplantation [21]. First, by performing an anti-BKV IFN- γ ELISPOT assay at the time that BK viruria or viremia is first detected. By this method one will be able to classify patients as having a positive or negative ELISPOT result. The former will be more likely to have self-limited BKV replication, transient BK viremia, and a good prognosis without substantial changes to their immunosuppressive treatment. On the contrary, patients with negative ELISPOT will possibly progress to persistent BK viremia or BKVAN and may therefore need more aggressive interventions [22]. Second, another suitable period is when immunosuppressive reduction has been implemented for the treatment of BKV infection. The IFN- γ ELISPOT assay could then serve as to guide the clinician whether or not to lower the immunosuppressive medications. Patients who have increasing numbers of IFN- γ pc to BKV continuously since the beginning of the intervention are more likely to eventually clear the virus. The number of BKV-specific IFN- γ pc that a clinician should target are depicted in Supplementary Figures S2 and S3 which should be accompanied by the patients' clinical course [23]. BKV-specific IFN- γ ELISPOT should be interpreted together with the BK viral load results. In current clinical practice, it is difficult to differentiate BK viremic patients who will achieve BK

viral clearance from those who will have progressive BK viremia leading to BKVAN. Knowing the ELISPOT result at the time of viral load testing, would allow clinicians to make informed decisions based on the patient's immune response against BKV [24]. Patients could then be stratified as high or low risk for developing BKVAN, and immunosuppression adjusted accordingly.

This add-on value of the ELISPOT to supplement BK viral load testing would help prevent unnecessary aggressive immunosuppression reduction that leads to concurrent or superimposed acute rejection in patients with BKV infection, a scenario which remains problematic in kidney transplantation. However, since there are variations of BKV-specific IFN- γ ELISPOT protocol among laboratories, including the type of BKV antigens used, the amount of recipient's PBMC used in the assay, and the cutoff values. Development of a standardized protocol with evidence-based threshold cutoffs to defined antigens and consistent PBMC concentrations is still needed before this method can be routinely applied in the clinics [25].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this meta-analysis and systematic review demonstrates that the IFN- γ ELISPOT assay is a useful tool for assessing the post-kidney transplantation risk of BKV-associated complications. Patients with an adequate T lymphocyte BKV-specific immune response (positive ELISPOT) are more likely to achieve resolution of BKV infection.

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